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An Assessment of Hazardous impacts of Coal Dust in Jharia Coal Field using GIS technique

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Jharia coalfield is probably one of the most talked about coal mining area not only in the country but also in many countries abroad due to its typical characteristics and unique status and problems. The coalfield has been witnessing mining since 1894 and is probably the most densely populated coal mining areas in the world. Air pollution in coal mines is mainly due to the fugitive emission of particulate matter and gases including methane (CH_4), sulfur dioxide (SO_2) and oxides of nitrogen (NO_x). The use of explosives releases carbon monoxide (CO), which poses a health risk for mine workers. Dust and coal particles stirred up during the mining process, as well as the soot released during coal transport, can cause severe and potentially deadly respiratory problems. High levels of suspended particulate matter increase respiratory diseases such as chronic bronchitis and asthma cases while gaseous emissions contribute towards global warming besides causing health hazards to the exposed population.

In this paper, an attempt has been made to visualize, analyze and assess the impacts of coal dust on densely populated areas of JCF using GIS techniques. In this research Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) in various point sources has been taken and interpolated to obtain the air quality status of JCF. Further, the various diseased prone areas due to coal dust have been mapped to obtain an assessment of the impacts of SPM over the densely populated areas of JCF.

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Abstract

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Keywords: JCF, SPM, Coal Dust, GIS.

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Introduction

Coal mining harms land, surface waters, groundwater and even our air. Impacts to the land from mining cause drastic changes in the local area. Damage to plants, animals and humans occurs from the destruction and removal of habitat and environmental contamination. Surface mining completely removes land from its normal uses. Property and scenic values are degraded as agricultural crops, forests, rangeland and deserts are replaced by pits, quarries and tailing piles. Underground mines not only impact groundwater hydrology, they are prone to subsidence. Further, mine wastes are generated in huge quantities. These wastes include the solid waste from the mine, called “gob,” refuse from coal washing and coal preparation, and the sludge from treating acid mine drainage. There are a number of environmental impacts from this waste generation. But the most grievous impact of coal mining is air pollution.

Air pollution in coal mines is mainly due to the fugitive emission of particulate matter and gases including methane (CH₄), sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and oxides of nitrogen

(NO_x). The use of explosives releases carbon monoxide (CO), which poses a health risk for mine workers. (*Health Aspects of Air Pollution with Particulate Matter, Ozone and Nitrogen Dioxide, Report of a WHO Working Group, Bonn, Germany January 2003.*) Dust and coal particles stirred up during the mining process, as well as the soot released during coal transport, can cause severe and potentially deadly respiratory problems. The mining operations like drilling, blasting, movement of the heavy earth moving machinery on haul roads, collection, transportation and handling of coal, screening, sizing and segregation units are the major sources of emissions and air pollution. Under-ground mine fire is also a major source of air pollution in some of the coal fields. High levels of suspended particulate matter increase respiratory diseases such as chronic bronchitis and asthma cases while gaseous emissions contribute towards global warming besides causing health hazards to the exposed population. Methane emission from coal mining depends on the mining methods, depth of coal mining, coal quality and entrapped gas content in coal seams.

Air pollution in JCF (Dhanbad District)

Mining and allied industries are the main sources of air pollution. Mining is carried out both by opencast and underground methods. The industries include thermal power stations, coal washeries, metal smelting plants, cement mills, coke oven and by-product plants, beehive coke oven and allied briquette plants, metal casting and steel rolling plants, refractories and engineering industries, stone crushers, line kiln, brick kilns etc. Dhanbad is rich in mineral resources and BCCL and CCL extensively carry out coal mining. Apart from coal mining other mining activities also exist. Opencast and underground mining methods are used for winning the minerals. Coal Dust is the major pollutant from these mines

Impacts of Coal Dust

Polluted air contains one, or more, hazardous substance, pollutant, or contaminant that creates a hazard to general health. It is usually measured in terms of "particulate matter", or, the number of particles of these potentially hazardous substances as a percentage of air. Coal dust suspended in air is explosive. Coal dust has far more surface area per unit weight than chunks of coal, and is more susceptible to spontaneous combustion. As a result, a nearly empty coal store is a greater explosion risk than a full one. The adverse effects on health of significant occupational exposure to coal dust have been well known for many years and have been well characterised in recent decades. (*M. Jennings and M. Flahive, Review of Health Effects Associated With Exposure to Inhalable Coal Dust, Coal Services Pty Ltd, October 2005*). Thus coal workers' pneumoconiosis (CWP) is a characteristic occupational disease involving chronic irritation of the lung resulting from coal dust inhalation. Associated with CWP, but also appearing in its absence, are conditions such as emphysema and chronic bronchitis which are also clearly linked, in terms of severity, with increasing exposure duration and/or airborne coal dust concentrations. (*J.M. Temple and A.M. Sykes, Asthma and Open Cast Mining, British Medical Journal 305, 396, 1992*). In addition, in about 1-2% of exposed persons with simple dust accumulation (simple CWP) solid, black masses develop which represent accumulations of coal dust in connective tissue. This condition is known as progressive

massive fibrosis (PMF). (*Health Aspects of Air Pollution with Particulate Matter, Ozone and Nitrogen Dioxide, Report of a WHO Working Group, Bonn, Germany January 2003*).

Methodology Adopted

In this research, SPM values in different locations of Dhanbad district collected by Central Institute of Mining and Fuel Research (CIMFR) and Bharat Coaking Coal Limited (BCCL) have been used for creating the geodatabase. Though, the SPM data collected for the entire Dhanbad district have been used to create the geodatabase, but specifically the data collected in Jharia Coal Field (JCF) has been mainly used. The database is then Normalized up to Third Normal Form (3NF) so as to eliminate any kind of insertion or updation anomalies. A global deterministic inexact spatial interpolation method Trend Surface Analysis is then used to estimate values at unknown points, i.e. other than control points and a surface data is being created. The third-order trend surface equation used in this approach is given below:

$$Z_{x,y}=b_0+b_1x+b_2y+b_3x^2+b_4xy+b_5y^2+b_6x^3+b_7x^2y+b_8xy^2+b_9y^3$$

where the attribute value Z is a function of x and y coordinates. The b coefficients are estimated from the known points. Next, the population density map of the whole Dhanbad district is prepared by using the Census data obtained from NRDMS Center, BIT Mesra, Ranchi. Another gaeodabse of percentage of diseases due to coal dust specifically pneumoconiosis is created using the data collected from DGMS, Dhanbad. Finally, the maps are spatially overlaid to obtain the areas of impacts of Coal dust.

Results and Analysis

The population density map of Dhanbad district is shown in figure **Fig 1**

Fig 1

The interpolated map to obtain the SPM distribution using Trend Surface Model is given in figure **Fig 2**

Fig 2

The average SPM value in different blocks of Dhanbad district is tabulated in Table 1:

BLOCK NAME	VALUE
TUNDI	47.28
TOPCHANCHI	101.72
GOVINDPUR	275.78
BHAGMARA	331.29
DHANBAD	411.21
JHARIA	537.22
BALIAPUR	407.25
NIRSA CUM CHIRKUNDA	456.78

Table 1: Average SPM values Block wise

The tabulated SPM values Block wise is depicted in **Chart 1**. Finally using the geodatabase of diseases and Spatial Overlaying of the Population Density Layer and SPM distribution layer the map of diseases is prepared which is shown in figure **Fig 3**

Chart 1. Average SPM values Blockwise

Fig 3 Disease Map Due to Coal Dust

From the above map, it's quite easy to comment about the fact that the regions where mining is continuously carried out are the places where the people are most affected by pneumoconiosis. But in this map, we can also see the nearby areas where we are getting positive results of persons suffering from this black disease. The reason there of is that

the particulate matter can float in air and reach nearby places very easily and quickly. This is the major concern regarding this, as not only the mine workers but the common persons living in nearby regions are also getting affected of this black disease.

Conclusion

There are adverse significant effects on health of occupational exposure to coal dust. Coal workers' pneumoconiosis is a characteristic occupational disease involving chronic irritation of the lung resulting from coal dust inhalation. Further, other diseases such as emphysema and chronic bronchitis, which are also clearly linked, in terms of severity, with increasing exposure duration and/or airborne coal dust are also affecting the health of not only mine workers, but people who are in the vicinity of mining areas. In addition, in about 1-2% of exposed persons with simple dust accumulation solid, black masses develop which represent accumulations of coal dust in connective tissue.

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